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Role of Responsibility Accounting in Achieving Competitive Advantage: A Case Study of Al-Amin Factory

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the importance of implementing of accountability in economic units and their role in achieving the competitiveness of economic units by dividing economic units into centers of responsibility, distributing functions and powers between centers and ensuring that each center proceeds as planned, This study was based on the hypothesis of information and reports provided by accountability to increase the effectiveness of economic units in promoting competitive advantage. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, an implementation was made to the (Al-Amin) Factory through the use of information provided by the factory including departmental reports (planning, human resources, finance, production) Determining the factory's positions of responsibility and building a proposed organizational structure and then applying the cost-leadership strategy that is a competitive advantage strategy, the study reached a number of important conclusions. The results of the evaluation of the profitability position performance showed negative results, as the value of the variable costs of products exceeded their revenues and thus could not cover their variable costs if the changing margin of contribution to the profit centers appeared (detergents, soaps, removers) negatively, as a result of poor strategy-building for marketing and production processes, The researcher recommends that the cost leadership strategy should be applied to the Soaps Production Section for its effectiveness in reducing the Centre costs if costs decrease by 57% resulting a change in the activity from loss to profit, with the need to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the production of preparations by conducting field studies of the reality of the demand for remarkable products, take into consideration comparable competitive products and relying on cost-cutting strategies and continuous improvement in the quality of products

Keywords: accountability system, competitive advantage, positions of responsibility, competitive strategies, performance calendar.

Study Structure

1.1 Study Problem

Although the size of economic units has evolved, interest in administrative accounting and its aspects in particular accountability has been very weak or inapplicable in some economic units. Despite its importance and effectiveness in helping the Department to eliminate daily burdens and problems, The establishment of an accounting framework based on centers of responsibility and the distribution of tasks is imperative to work to

motivate the employees of the economic unit to do what they are mandated to do and increase their sense of responsibility towards the economic unit. Next is to enhance the level of financial and administrative performance, especially if the economic units focus on achieving and strengthening competitive advantage and the importance of using and applying one of the administrative accounting tools of: (responsibility accounting System) in order to achieve growth and development in economic units, and the need to increase coordination between the responsibility positions in economic units, clarify their mutual relationships and enhance cooperation to raise performance levels. In addition, it is necessary to direct the Centre of Responsibility managers to conduct performance evaluations in economic units and to ensure alignment with predetermined objectives and actual achievements.

Based on the above, the basic research problem can be formulated:

(Does the Implementing of Responsibility Accounting system contribute to achieving competitive advantage?).

1.2 Study hypothesis

The research is based on the main hypothesis:

(The Implementing of Responsibility Accounting system can support the achievement of competitive advantage in economic units)

There are the following hypotheses:

1. The information and reports provided by accountability increase the effectiveness of economic units in enhancing competitive advantage.
2. There is a relationship between defining responsibilities and duties between departments in economic units and enhancing competitive advantage.
3. The accountability system increases the effectiveness and efficiency of performance and thus enhances the competitive advantage of economic units.

1.3 Study Objectives

As a result of the expansion and development of the investment sector, competition in the industrial sector has increased. if the research aims to determine the relevance of the application of accountability in economic units and their role in achieving the competitive advantage of economic units, by dividing economic units into centers of responsibility, distributing functions and powers between centers and ensuring that each center proceeds as planned, the objectives of the research are:

1. Address the importance of applying accountability in economic units and their role in achieving competitive advantage.
2. Highlight the positions of responsibility, and ensure that commitment is available in applying the policies and objectives of economic unity.
3. Identify the extent to which accountability is applied in economic units.
4. Know the impact of applying and using accountability in economic units and their objective in achieving competitive advantage in the industrial sector.

1.4 Importance of Study

The importance of research is highlighted by the use of a new system in administrative accounting known as (Responsibility Accounting system), the research aims to clarify the importance of applying Responsibility

accounting system within economic units by harmonizing the Responsibility positions of each department within the economic unit; This instrument seeks to assess the impact of the application of the Responsibility accounting system on enhancing productivity and thereby promoting competitive advantage. Furthermore, the research provides a new framework for exploring variables, particularly the role of accountability in enhancing competitive advantage. Interdepartmental self-regulation and internal competition within the unit were heightened due to the emphasis on accountability adoption by economic units. This in turn promotes an enabling environment for enhancing external competition within the industry sector, thereby increasing profitability compared to competing entities.

1.5 Study Methodology

In order to achieve the research objectives, the researcher followed the extractive approach of building and identifying the axes and chapters of the study and formulating her hypotheses the historical approach to tracking previous studies, while the inductive approach was relied on to diagnose the nature of the relationship between accountability (independent variable) and competitive advantage (dependent variable).

1.6 Study Sources

In order to cover the theoretical and practical aspects of this study, the following sources were relied upon for the required data and information:

1. Methodological books in Arabic and English.
2. University theses and theses related to study variables at the local and international level.
3. Research and scientific articles published in academic journals and local and international conferences.
4. International Information Network (Internet).
5. Records, reports and financial statements of the company in question.
6. Field visits and personal interviews with a number of relevant parties of the company in question.

1.7 Study Model

2.1 Concept of accountability

Accountability was accompanied by the evolution of administrative accounting and management and financial information systems in order to meet the needs of management and become instrumental in evaluating and controlling the performance of economic units and using available resources in order to increase competition in the industrial sector and thus work to increase productivity by supporting the spirit of innovation to reach the best use of available resources and energy.

(Husain, Mahdawi, 2021:452).

This can be explained by presenting some definitions of a Responsibility accounting system in the following table:

Table 1. Concept of a Responsibility accounting system

Source	Conception	Author	N
(Tran ,Dinha,Alt.,2020: 611)	A system that is applied within the economic unit to collect and report expenses for each administrative level within the unit. Each manager must be responsible for the control of his expenses allocated to him	Huygens 1952.	1
(Atu,Omimi-Ejoor Osaretin Kingsley,2014: 74)	An accounting system that separates costs from income related to each subsection within the Economic Unit in order to evaluate and control the performance of people who have been tasked with carrying out responsibilities and directed authorities. The Institute also indicated that it can be defined as activity accounting that is used to monitor all decentralized	(CIMA)	2

	processes.		
(Yisa, Ishola, 2020:93)	A system applied to study the relationship between activities and the performance of those activities associated with each department so that they can be easily evaluated through the method of decentralization within the economic unit, thereby effectively contributing to the evaluation of the performance of the departments	Biswas, 2017	4
(12 : 2020 • Tawill)	A system for compiling accounting information and conducting the process of examining accounting data and then analysing and presenting them by submitting reports that include the responsibility of individuals towards their duties in order to achieve the effectiveness of oversight and performance evaluation, which helps management focus on the decision-making process in the development of operational plans and budgets and follow up on its first implementation process.	•Tawill 2020	6

2.2 Requirements for application of Responsibility accounting system

The application of Responsibility accounting in economic units requires the availability of many elements that help to effectively apply Responsibility accounting, as each system includes many procedures and tools.

The requirements for applying Responsibility accounting are as follows:

A good and understandable organizational structure: The accountability system depends on the existence of an organizational structure of the Confederate Unit, where accountability represents a responsibility as one of the control tools that clarifies the responsibilities and powers of each administrative level, center of responsibility or individual where it constitutes an organizational map called (Responsibility map) That shows the role and importance of each level of administration and work to assess the performance of the departments during the productive and administrative stages and clarify the interdependence between the departments, and therefore for the purpose of applying accountability of Responsibility must have a clear organizational structure that is characterized as the most important of which is the delegation of powers and responsibilities within the economic unit. (Aoun, 2019:44)

Identification of Responsibility positions: Responsibility centers are linked to the organizational structure of the economic unit, and for the purpose of applying accountability requires an organizational structure that clarifies the centers of responsibility and authorities and takes into account the equal opportunity to be an objective accountability and performance control process (Sharif, 2018:370). Responsibility centers will be addressed in detail at the end of the research.

Accounting system: The accounting system is defined as the organizational structure's statute, which is based on the use of available resources and conversion into information intended to satisfy the needs of users entering and exiting for the purpose of assisting them in the decision-making process (Rahman, Al-Shamrani, 2018: 13), the researcher defines the accounting system as a set of methods and procedures that regulate the conduct of financial and administrative operations within the economic unit and represents the performance through which the positions of responsibility are monitored by the responsible body, by choosing an accounting system appropriate to the nature of the economic unit's activity.

Planning budgets: Planning budgets are the key to financial management that helps it to understand and estimate future operations as they work to sustain the AU in the future through vision and planning for the future, as they serve as a translation of the plans developed by estimating the funds that will be spent to accomplish the

established activities. (Cost Center), funds to be generated from these activities (Revenue Center), and thus the budgets form the basis of the Responsibility accounting application whereby the planned performance is evaluated by actual results (civicus, 2001).

2.3 Responsibility Accounting Centers

The organizational structure of the economic unit is only an arrangement of lines of responsibility within the economic unit. Large-sized economic units, organize their activities by organizing administrative and productive departments with each responsible manager with decision-making authority. Each manager, regardless of his or her level of administration, is responsible for a particular responsibility center.

Thus, Responsibility positions can be defined as part, segment or subdivision of an institution whose director is responsible for a specific set of activities, as accountability for Responsibility is only a system that measures the plans, budgets, procedures and actual results of each Responsibility center. (Horngren's, 2018: 237-238)

There are four types of positions of responsibility:

1. Cost Centre - Manager is responsible for costs only.
2. Revenue Centre - Director is responsible for revenue only.
3. Profit Centre - Director is responsible for income and costs.
4. Investment Centre - Director responsible for investments, income and costs.

2.4 Competitive Advantage Concept

Many economic units provide services and products that exceed consumers' expectations as compared to similar offers to competitors, with multiple definitions of competitive advantage. The concept of competitive advantage will be defined by the following:

1. The ability of the economic unit to achieve superior performance over its competitors to achieve the purpose of increasing the profitability of the economic unit (Helena, 2019:71).
2. Outperform competitors by building a loyal customer base by reducing prices for products and increasing product efficiency. (Ehmke,2015:1-2)
3. Business sustainability in terms of the organization's ability to distinguish itself from other competitors, thus serving as the basis for designing business strategies to achieve sustainable growth in the trade units of all sizes. (Potjanajaruwit,2018:106)
4. Being able to stay ahead of current or potential competition, so the superior performance reached through competitive advantage will ensure staying in the market. (Wang,Lin,elt ,2011:100)
5. The organization's ability to gain a share in the full competition market and its ability to survive and maintain its market share, by achieving high profit rates through an increase in its sales, i.e., the competitive advantage shows the extent to which the essential elements within the economic unit are available to it to continue and remain in the competition market. (Ramadan, 2021: 36-37)

2.5 Strategies for achieving competitive advantage

Porter has developed a system based on three general strategies that are used by economic units to achieve their objective: (Maintaining competitive advantage) General strategies are based on two dimensions (The scope of the strategy, the strength of the strategy) The first is after the demand side and the last after the supply side. These strategies are applied at the business unit level. Porter explains that economic units with a high market share were yielding because they followed a strategy (cost leadership)

Units with low market share were successful because they used market segmentation, that is, concentrated on a small but profitable market category, and economic units in the middle were less profitable because they did not follow a viable strategy. Porter noted that the combination of successful strategies occurs in only one case is the combination of (Market segmentation strategy with product differentiation) but combining strategy (Cost leadership and product differentiation) is very difficult but not impossible and this happens due to the conflict between cost reduction and the additional cost of product differentiation (Tanwar,2013:11-12) and will be addressed in detail through the following:

First: Differentiation Strategy

This strategy includes selecting one or more standards used by buyers in the market, and then determining the company's unique position to meet those standards. This strategy usually goes hand in hand with the imposition of a premium price on the product - often to reflect higher production costs and additional advantages offered to the consumer. Discrimination is about charging a premium price that exceeds additional production costs, and providing clear reasons for customers to prefer the product to other equally undistinguished products. Companies that succeed in the discrimination strategy often enjoy the following internal forces: (Wang, Lin, et, 2011:102)

- Ability to innovate: Ability to develop and deliver unique and innovative products or services that exceed customers' expectations.
- High quality: Ability to provide high quality products or services that outperform competition in performance, durability and responsibility.
- Expertise: Ability to provide a skilled and experienced team that can achieve differentiation in production or service delivery.
- Marketing and brand capacity: The ability to effectively promote and market the product and build a strong brand makes consumers prefer the product to compete.

Second: Cost leadership strategy

It helps reduce the threat of new companies entering by creating cost barriers to entry, such as economies of volume of production and non-volume cost advantages. Cost reduction also reduces the threat of competition through pricing strategies that low-cost companies can enter. If the company can achieve overall cost leadership, its performance will be above average. The logic of the cost leadership strategy usually requires the company to be a cost leader. When there is more than one competitor aspiring to achieve cost leadership, the competition between them is usually high, and companies that succeed in achieving the cost strategy often have the following internal strengths: (Javadi,2020: 17)

1-Skill in product design, ability to reduce components to reduce cost and reduce production time.

2-High level of experience in the production and distribution process.

3-Ability to make significant investment in capital and assets that constitute a barrier to entry for many companies.

Third: Focus Strategy

The focus strategy refers to the identification of a specific group of customers or target market to develop products or services in order to better meet the needs of this category of competitors where the focus answers the following points: (Michael,2016:20)

1-Market Analysis: The market must be analyzed and studied to reach customers' needs to provide products and services that meet their requirements and thus maintain the company's market share.

2-Identifying the target group: focusing on a particular category of customers and identifying their needs and preferences to promote understanding of the target audience.

3-Customize the product or service: By developing a specific strategy for the design and implementation of the product or service to suit the customer's requirements.

A focus strategy in a particular category helps the company build competitive excellence and distinction in the market by better meeting the needs and desires of targeted customers than competitors in the market.

3. Study methodology

To achieve the objectives of the study and to tell its basic hypotheses, the researcher evaluates the performance of the centers of responsibility and determines their deviations by relying on the information provided by the factory and then applying the cost leadership strategy to reduce the cost of the center of responsibility for profitability.

1.3 Financial indicators : To determine the company's financial situation, its financial indicators, consisting of a set of financial impact indicators, must be analyzed:

1. Factory expenses: Al-Amin, an essential plant in the State Company for the Manufacture of Vegetable Oils, produces a range of products that affect the company's budget. The factory seeks to minimize costs, while maintaining quality according to approved standards, and achieving profit margin.

Table No. (1) Factory expenses for the years 2020 – 2022

Previous year's growth ratio	2022	Previous year's growth ratio	2021	2020	Account name	Account number
-2%	6,882,443	-2%	6,993,174	7,127,246	Employees' salaries	311
-5%	669,257	6%	704,505	662,276	Contribution to social security	312
-2%	7,551,700	-1%	7,697,679	7,789,522	Salaries	31
55%	343,455	16%	221,826	191,062	Raw Material	321
18%	241,481	6%	204,901	193,048	Fuel & Oil	322
32%	105,670	8%	80,123	73,991	Spare tools	323
22%	105,551	3%	86,486	84,166	Packaging & Packaging Materials	324
27%	23,088	32%	18,238	13,772	Miscellaneous	325
17%	6,373	-1%	5,464	5,496	Workers' Equipment	326
-20%	42,592	-26%	53,508	72,556	Water & Electricity	327
65%	1,344,471	28%	812,834	634,091	Commodity Supplies	32
-19%	140,581	15%	174,032	150,997	Maintenance Services	331
36%	1,980	-18%	1,461	1,790	Bruises Research and Consulting	332
7%	16,389	35%	15,338	11,361	Publicity, Printing and Hospitality	333
8%	195,795	20%	181,800	150,975	Transport, dispatch and communication	334
19%	3,641	1%	3,055	3,033	Rent of fixed assets	335
86%	81,354	29%	43,791	33,816	Service expenses	336
-2%	400,740	16%	409,477	351,973	Service Supplies	33
2%	396,808	5%	390,034	370,025	Extinction	37
66%	37,314	46%	22,502	15,384	Transfer expenses	38
31%	3,910	16%	2,990	2,572	Other expenses	39
4%	9,770,139	2%	9,352,426	9,163,567	Total Expenses	

Source: Researcher's preparation based on the comparison of the finance department

By analyzing the factory's expense account for the years 2020 - 2022, the following are shown:

- A decrease in the calculation of salaries overall years due to the high rate of employee retirement, as the number of employees for 2021 decreased by 19 employees and 22 employees for 2022.
 - A rise in the calculation of commodity supplies overall years due to an increase in the purchase of raw materials, spare tools and packaging materials, rising by 28% in 2021 and 65% in 2022.
 - Service supplies increased by 16% in 2021 due to a rise in maintenance expenses, hospitality expenses and IFAD expenses, unlike 2022, where we note a decrease in service expenses by 2% due to a 19% decrease in maintenance expenses.
 - Despite fluctuations in the proportion of sub-expenses for the years 2020-2022, the final result is a rise in total factory expenses by 2% for 2021 and 4% for 2022.
2. Factory revenues: The oil sector revenues of the General Company for Food Products constitute 20% to 37%. The Al Amin Factory is the second most important oil production plant. Its revenues for 2022 accounted for 33% of other factory revenues.

Table No. (2) Factory revenues for the years 2020 – 2022

Previous year's growth ratio	2022	Previous year's growth ratio	2021	2020	Account name	Account number
161%	2,305,731	49%	882,732	592,719	Commodity Activity Income	41
%9-	21,186	%7-	23,221	25,064	Service Activity Income	43
	-		-		Activity income to others	44
	-		-		Locally manufactured assets	45
	-		2,500		Benefits and leases of land	46
-4%	7,513,551	-10%	7,799,654	8,622,725	Conversion income	48
49%	4,925	-55%	3,298	7,305	Other revenues	49
	9,845,393		8,713,404	9,247,814	Total	

Source: Researcher's preparation based on the comparison of the finance department

Based on the data provided in the table, the following can be concluded:

- Continued growth with commodity activity, rising 49% in 2021 and 161% in 2022 indicating strong and sustainable growth.
- A decrease in the revenue of service activity by 7% in 2021. This decrease continued in 2022, as the rate of decline rose to 9%, which is not a positive indicator for the company.
- Some items have experienced significant changes, such as interest and rents that fell 100% in 2022, and transformational revenue that decreased 10% in 2021 and 4% in 2022.
- Significant growth in other revenues, falling 55% in 2021, and then rising 49% in 2022.

Using the data of tables 1 and 2, the result of the activity under way for the years 2020 - 2022 can be shown through the following table:

Table No. (3) Result of factory activity for the years 2020-2022

Previous year's growth ratio	2022	Previous year's growth ratio	2021	2020	Account name
13%	9,845,393	-6%	8,711,404	9,247,814	Current activity income
4%	9,770,139	2%	9,352,426	9,163,567	Cost of current activity
	75,254		(641,022)	84,247	

Source: Researcher's preparation based on Table No. (1) (2)

From the previous table can be inferred as follows:

- A decrease in factory revenues for 2021 by 6% and a rise in the cost of activity by 2%, which explains the reason for the deficit for 2021 as opposed to the previous year, where it made a profit of 1%.
- A rise in the company's revenue for 2022 by 13%, accompanied by a rise in the cost of the activity by 4%, but the rise in costs did not affect the result of the activity, as the factory made a profit of 1% and we conclude that the margin of contribution of the factory is 1%.

2.3 Calendar Performance Center Profitability

Table (3) Profitability Center Performance Calendar 2022

Center for Profitability Responsibility								Total	Centre Process
		Process of producing remover		Soap Production Process		Detergent Production Process			Activities
packing	manufacturing	Preparation	Cutting, forming and packing	Preparation and mixing	packing	dehydration	Active substance		
					40,077	193,083	44,361	277,521.00	Centre's income
							variable costs	3,441,222	Employees' cash salaries
491,603	491,603	393,282	491,603	393,282	491,603	294,962	393,282	171,728	Raw Material Ores
24,533	24,533	19,626	24,533	19,626	24,533	14,720	19,626	52,835	Spare tools
7,548	7,548	6,038	7,548	6,038	7,548	4,529	6,038	52,775	Packaging & Packaging Materials
7,539	7,539	6,031	7,539	6,031	7,539	4,524	6,031	21,296	Water & Electricity
3,042	3,042	2,434	3,042	2,434	3,042	1,825	2,434	8,194	Publicity, Printing and Hospitality
1,171	1,171	936	1,171	936	1,171	702	936	153,764	Fuel & Oil
21,345	21,601	17,895	21,345	17,895	21,345	14,445	17,895	3,901,814	Total
556,780	557,036	446,243	556,780	446,243	556,780	335,707	446,243	3,901,814	Total variable costs
					1,113,817	1,449,267	1,338,730	(3,624,293.22)	Variable contribution margin
	(1,073,740)		-	(1,256,184)	-	-	(1,294,369)		

Through the above table, the following is inferred: -

- The profit center (detergent) which is concerned with the production of (car wash rim, carpet cleaner, washing soap) Showed negative results as the Centre's revenue from the sale of products) 44,361 (IQD 1,000) and the variable center costs (1,338,730) amounted to IQD 1,000. This indicates that the product

costs are higher than its revenue. The products cannot cover the variable costs and consequently have achieved a loss of IQD 1,294,369.

- The Profit Center (Soaps) which is concerned with the production of (Laurel soap, toilet soap, liquid soap) showed negative results as the Centre's revenue from the sale of products (193,083 IQD and the variable center costs (IQD 1,449,267) This indicates that the product costs are higher than its revenue, i.e., the products cannot cover the variable costs and consequently achieved a loss of IQD 1,256,184.
- The Profit Centre (Removers), which is concerned with the production of (Calculus Remover, zetol) showed negative results, with the Centre's revenues from the sale of products (IQD 40,077 thousand and variable status costs(1,113,817)A thousand IQD. This indicates that the product costs are higher than its revenues. The products cannot cover the variable costs. Consequently, they have achieved a loss of 1,073,740 IQD.
- The margin of contribution of variable profit centers (detergents, soaps, removers) appears negative. This means that the variable costs of products are higher than the product's sales revenues. The main reason is that the sale price of products is not sufficient to cover the variable costs associated with its production. This indicates that: -
 - The product being sold is unprofitable.
 - There is no study of the product's selling prices and associated costs in the market.
 - Weakness in building strategies for marketing and production operations.
 - The negative variable contribution margin directly affects the performance of the profit center because it shows the center's inability to cover the variable costs only and does not contribute to the profitability of the company.

Focusing on the second sub-hypothesis of the research, which states that reports to be provided by accountancy enhance competitive advantage and refer to the primary objective of the research based on the identification of appropriate accounting measures to enhance the unit's competitive advantage and given the difficulty of applying a differentiation strategy and cost leadership At the same time, the researcher proposes to apply a cost leadership strategy based on accountability reports to reduce the cost and thus increase the profitability of the company that will work in parallel with enhancing the competitive advantage. The primary purpose of cost reduction is to report to senior management and shareholders to assist in the decision-making process and to rely on the theoretical aspect of the second research in chapter II. Focusing on the center of profitability because it is the center that has not achieved the expected profit as a result of the higher variable costs of the center and relying on the cost leadership strategy, the costs that add value to the product will be determined and separated from the costs that do not add value to the product, as costs that do not add value to the product will be excluded. The purpose of this strategy is to increase the profitability of the plant and will be applied through the following: -

Reduction in the costs of the production center of soaps, detergents and removers, where we note that the costs of revenue are very high and after auditing and conducting personal interviews with factory officials show the following: -

The calculation of salaries includes the salaries of the private sector of the oil industry and female employees due to the use of the central system of the company and after an audit the amount was found to include the salaries of the Ameen factory and other oil factories (Rashid, Ma 'amun) after an audit with the financial department of the company.

After interviewing officials at the plant and through field visits to the plant, the actual number of workers at the plant was found (250) Workers not included in the reports of the Planning Section and after the audit found that the difference made (110) are workers appointed as contract at the plant and (140) workers are solely on permanent owners, due to weak control and control by officials, the failure to properly distribute tasks and

powers to managers and the failure to apply the decentralization system as the factory relies on the factory manager to make decisions for all departments.

The incentive allowances for workers in the factory as well as overtime were included in the calculation of salaries resulting in a higher amount of the worker's salary and thus difficulty in determining the costs to be reduced by the factory officials.

Based on the above data, the actual productivity of workers will be determined according to the actual working hours of each quarter of the year and subsequently the surplus of workers that does not produce but only increases in factory costs.

5. Application of Cost Leadership Strategy

1.5 Salary Account Reduction

After consulting the data of the list (expenses for 2022) Table No. (1) and considering the distribution to the Centre of Responsibility for Profitability and after checking the actual number of works of the factory, the calculation of salaries can be reduced through the following: -

Schedule (4) Reduction of salary calculation

rate of reduction	Calculation of salaries after reduction	Calculation of salaries before reduction	Amount of reduction	Actual number of workers	Department
72%	109,753	393,282.46	31	43	Detergent
70%	89,382	294,961.84	23	33	Soaps
58%	194,120	458,829.53	30	52	Removers

2. Reduce the calculation of backup tools

after checking with the management of the factory show that some places are not working and are not used by the Center. They cause a cost to the Center without generating revenues for the Center, as shown in the table below:

Table (5) Reduction of Backup Tools Account

rate of reduction	Calculate reserve tools after reducing	Calculate reserve tools before reducing	Amount of reduction	Actual number of machines	Department
36%	11,528	18,114.86	4	11	Detergent
43%	7,764	13,586.14	3	7	Soaps
31%	14,631	21,134.00	4	13	Removers

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table data (3)

Table above shows the reduction in the number of redundant machines. The impact of the decrease in their numbers on the spare tools is reflected, we note that the cost of the detergent section decreased by 36% as a result of the decrease in the number of machines from 11 machines to 7 machines. The cost of the removers section decreased by 43% as a result of the decrease in the number of machines from 7 machines to 4 machines, The cost of the removal section decreased by 31% as a result of the decrease in the number of machines from 13 machines to 9 machines. "cost-driving strategy", the application of the cost-driving strategy requires management to reduce the cost commensurate with the quality of the products.

5.3 Packing and packaging materials

After conducting enquiries and interviews with officials at the factory, it was found that the packaging materials are purchased by the Maamoun factory, one of the factories of the State Company for Food Products, so the researcher proposes to buy them from the factory at the cost because it is considered one of the company's sister factories and refer to the special data of the cost of packaging materials showing the following:

Table (6) Reduced calculation of packaging materials

rate of reduction	Cost of production from AL-Maamoun factory	Cost of purchasing from Al Amin Factory	Department
20%			Detergent

	14,491.89	18,114.86	
20%	10,856.65	13,570.81	Soaps
20%	16,888.13	21,110.16	Removers

Source: Student's preparation based on table data (3)

Through the above schedule, we note that the decrease was by the profit margin set by the management of the AL-Maamoun, which decreased by 20% for the three divisions. This decrease contributes to the reduction of cost and thus affects the profitability of the products.

5.4 Reduce the calculation of water and electricity

The calculation of water and electricity of the Centre of Responsibility for Profitability represents the costs spent on productive departments and after interviews and enquiries from officials within the plant and comparing the actual working hours of the plant with the number of machineries actually operated shows a decrease in the rate of working hours and consequently lower costs related to the calculation according to the following table:

Table (7) Reduction in the calculation of water and electricity

rate of reduction	Calculation of electricity and water after reduction	Calculation of electricity and water before reduction	amount of reduction	Actual number of machines	Department
36%	4,646	7,301.54	4	11	Detergent
43%	3,129	5,476.16	3	7	Soaps
31%	5,897	8,518.47	4	13	Removers

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table (3)

Through the above table we note the low cost of calculating water and electricity based on the indicator of decrease in machinery the impact of their lower numbers on the calculation of water and electricity We note that the cost of the detergent section decreased by 36% due to the decrease in the number of machines from 11 machines to 7 workers, The cost of the soaps section decreased by 43% as a result of the decrease in the number

of machines from 7 to 4 machines The cost of the removal section decreased by 31% as a result of the decrease in the number of machines from 13 to 9 machines, Applying the cost leadership strategy requires management to reduce the cost in proportion to the quality of the products.

5.5 Account Publicity, Printing and Hospitality

The above account represents an additional expense of the Centre for the Responsibility of Profitability because it does not enter the production of the products of the factory, so it must not be added to the expenses of the Center to reduce the costs of the products, so the Center for the Responsibility of Profitability of the Productive Divisions will be reduced by the following amounts: -

Table (8) Amount of reduction of publicity, printing and hospitality account

Reduction amount	Department
2,809.49	Detergent
2,107.11	Soaps
3,277.73	Removers

Source: Applicant's preparation based on table data (3)

5.6 Payment of fuel and oil

The CPC's fuel and oil calculation represents the costs spent on productive departments and after interviews and inquiries from officials within the plant and comparison with the number of machines actually operated shows lower costs related to the calculation according to the following table:

Table (9) Low calculation of fuel and oil

Reduction Ratio	Calculation of petrol and oil after reduction	Petrol and oil account before reduction	Amount of reduction	Actual number of machines	Department
36%	34,163	53,684.69	4	11	Detergent
43%	22,423	39,239.51	3	7	Soaps
31%	42,120	60,840.13	4	13	Removers

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table (3)

Table above shows the reduction in the number of redundant machines The impact of the decrease in their numbers is reflected in the calculation of fuel and oil, we note that the cost of the detergent section decreased by 36% as the number of machines decreased from 11 to 7 machines the cost of the soaps section decreased by

43% as a result of the reduction in the number of machines from 7 to 4 machines, The cost of the removal section decreased by 31% as a result of the decrease in the number of machines from 13 machines to 9 machines cost, the implementing of the cost-leadership strategy requires management to reduce the cost commensurate with the quality of the products.

6. Comparative Analysis of Profitability Center Before and After Application of Cost Leadership Strategy

Based on the above, the profitability center departments will be compared before and after the application of the cost leadership strategy to measure its impact on the profitability of the department.

1.6 Division Detergent

Detergent section costs related to the section's specific activity (active substance activity, drying activity, packing activity) were reduced by 58% for total costs as follows: -

Table (10) Comparison of detergent section after application of cost driving strategy

Reduction Ratio	After Reduction	Before Reduction	Account	Production Section
72%	109,753	393,282.46	Employees' cash salaries	Detergent
0%	58,878.00	58,878.00	Raw Material Ores	
36%	11,528	18,114.86	Spare tools	
20%	14,491.89	18,094.42	Packaging & Packaging Materials	
36%	4,646	7,301.54	Water & Electricity	
100%	0	2,809.49	Publicity, Printing and Hospitality	
36%	34,163	53,684.69	Fuel & Oil	
58%	233,460	552,165.45		Total
	44,361	44,361		Revenues
	(189,098.94)	(507,804.45)		Profit

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table (3) and (4-9) data

Through the above table we note the following: -

1. The cost of calculating salaries decreased by 72%, after reducing the number of redundant workers.
2. There is no change in the calculation of raw material ores because it is an account related to purchases of materials from the domestic or foreign market.
3. The cost of calculating the reserve tools decreased by 36%, after reducing the number of discontinued machines.
4. The cost of packaging materials decreased by 20%, after the purchase of materials at cost from the processor (AL-Maamoun Factory).
5. The cost of calculating water and electricity decreased by 36%, after reducing the number of interrupted machines.
6. Delete advertising, printing and hospitality account costs because they are not related to the production department and convert them to the marketing department.
7. The fuel and oil account decreased by 36%, after reducing the number of discontinued machines.
8. After calculating the profitability of the department, we note that the amount of loss decreased by 63%.

2.6 Surface Section

The section costs related to the section's specific activity (mixing activity, cutting, forming and packing activity) were reduced by 57% for total costs as follows: -

Table (11) Comparison of the soaps Section after applying a cost leadership strategy

Reduction Ratio	After Reduction	Before Reduction	Account	Production Section
70%	89,382	294,961.84	Employees' cash salaries	soaps
0%	44,158.50	44,158.50	Raw Material Ores	
43%	7,764	13,586.14	Spare tools	
20%	10,856.65	13,570.81	Packaging & Packaging Materials	
43%	3,129	5,476.16	Water & Electricity	
100%		2,107.11	Publicity, Printing and Hospitality	
43%	22,423	39,239.51	Fuel & Oil	
57%	177,713	413,100.09		
	193,083	193,083		Revenues
	15,370.15	(220,017.09)		Profit

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table (3) and (4-9) data

Through the above table we note the following: -

1. The cost of calculating salaries decreased by 70%, after reducing the number of redundant workers.
2. There is no change in the calculation of raw material ores because it is an account related to purchases of materials from the domestic or foreign market.
3. The cost of calculating the reserve tools decreased by 43%, after reducing the number of discontinued machines.
4. The cost of packaging materials decreased by 20%, after the purchase of materials at cost from the processor (AL-Maamoun Factory).
5. The cost of calculating water and electricity decreased by 43%, after reducing the number of interrupted machines.
6. Delete advertising, printing and hospitality account costs because they are not related to the production department and convert them to the marketing department.

7. The fuel and oil account decreased by 43%, after reducing the number of discontinued machines.
8. The result of the activity changed from loss to profit as the profitability rate was 9% of the division's costs.

3.6 Removers Section

The costs of the removal section related to the section's specific activity (preparation activity, manufacturing activity, packing activity) were reduced by 49% for the total costs as follows: -

Table (12) Comparison of Remover Section after application of Cost Driving Strategy

Reduction Ratio	After Reduction	Before Reduction	Account	Production Section
58%	194,120	458,829.53	Employees' cash salaries	Removers
0%	68,691.00	68,691.00	Raw Material Ores	
31%	14,631	21,134.00	Spare tools	
20%	16,888.13	21,110.16	Packaging & Packaging Materials	
31%	5,897	8,518.47	Water & Electricity	
100%	0	27,380.79	Publicity, Printing and Hospitality	
31%	42,120	60,840.13	Fuel & Oil	
49%	342,348	666,504.08		Total
	40,077	40,077		Revenues
	(302,271.04)	(626,427.08)		Profit

Source: Researcher's preparation based on table (3) and (4-9) data

Through the above table we note the following: -

1. The cost of calculating salaries decreased by 58%, after reducing the number of redundant workers.
2. There is no change in the calculation of raw material ores because it is an account related to purchases of materials from the domestic or foreign market.
3. The cost of calculating the reserve tools decreased by 31%, after reducing the number of discontinued machines.
4. The cost of packaging materials decreased by 20%, after the purchase of materials at cost from the processor (AL-Maamoun Factory).
5. The cost of calculating water and electricity decreased by 31%, after reducing the number of interrupted machines.
6. Delete advertising, printing and hospitality account costs because they are not related to the production department and convert them to the marketing department.
7. The fuel and oil account decreased by 49%, after reducing the number of interrupted machines.
8. After calculating the profitability of the department, we note that the amount of loss decreased by 52%.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

The results of the profitability center's performance evaluation showed negative results as the value of the variable costs of products exceeded their revenues and thus could not cover their variable costs if the changing

margin of contribution of profit centers (detergents, soaps, removals) appeared negative, as a result of weak strategy building for marketing and production operations.

After interviewing officials and field visits to the factory, we find a weakness in planning, human resources and financial reports.

The reports of the General Company for Food Products do not present a realistic picture of the performance of the plant and lack many requirements to be provided to measure the result of the plant's activity.

The need to link accountability with competitive advantage in the manner in which the following are achieved:

To ensure full control of the activities carried out in the centers of responsibility and in a way that improves the standards of costs and makes them more fair and objective, while constantly updating the cost orientations, which are the factors influencing the cost increase and decrease, and which reflect their impact on the application of the competitive advantage strategy of cost leadership.

Provide more detailed information on all processes and mutual relationships within the economic unit through detailed analysis of all activities, allowing for more effective control and reduction of cost by supporting and increasing the effectiveness of value-hosting activities and eliminating activities that do not add value, which is reflected in the competitive advantage of the economic unit.

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